

EMOTIONAL-EXPRESSIVE CAUSATIVE VERBS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK**Musaev Abish Abilkazievich**

Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6985369>

Abstract. This article deals with the causative emotionality in the English and Karakalpak languages that represents different structure from each other. Moreover, it shows that the positive causative emotionality has the semantics of intentionality in a certain sense. The causation of the subject in order to influence the addressee also represents intentional causative emotionality. In the given examples taken from English and Karakalpak literatures, positive and negative emotive causative verbs were highlighted.

Keywords: causative, emotionality, lexical, morphological, analytical, positive, negative.

ЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНО-ЭКСПРЕССИВНЫЕ КАУЗАТИВНЫЕ ГЛАГОЛЫ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И КАРАКАЛПАКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается каузативная эмоциональность в английском и каракалпакском языках, которые представляют собой отличную друг от друга структуру. Более того, он показывает, что положительная каузативная эмоциональность в определенном смысле обладает семантикой интенциональности. Причинение субъекта с целью воздействия на адресата также представляет собой интенциональную каузативную эмоциональность. В приведенных примерах, взятых из английской и каракалпакской литературы, выделены положительные и отрицательные эмотивные каузативные глаголы.

Ключевые слова: каузативность, эмоциональность, лексическая, морфологическая, аналитическая, положительная, отрицательная.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important processes in the life of mankind is speech communication. In the process of speech, various emotional situations and expressive relationships arise between individuals. Emotions and expressive attitudes have a great influence on the thoughts, views and actions of individuals. That is why types of emotive-expressive expressions are studied and researched in various fields.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Emotional-expressive expression is evaluated as a universal phenomenon, and linguistic research is conducted at many levels. Therefore, the comparative analysis of emotional units serves to reveal not only the way of expression of language units in English and Karakalpak languages, but also the linguistic and cultural features of those languages, their activation in specific structures. In addition to the fact that emotional-expressive units have their own characteristics in both languages, there are also aspects related to causative semantics. Causative emotiveness in English and Karakalpak languages is fundamentally different in terms of cognitive, semantic and expressive methods, and according to the plan of expression.

In the works related to the phenomenon of emotionality, the opposition related to the expression of emotionality, i.e. dividing into types such as positive, negative, and sometimes pleasant, unpleasant, has become a broad research. "Any emotion has a label and belongs to one of the emotional groups such as positive, negative or ambivalent" [1: 110-115]. According to linguists, the linguistic description of emotionality is based on whether a person feels "good"

(experiencing positive emotions such as joy, pride) or "bad" (fear, anger, shame) situations [2: 31-41]. In particular, A.L. Groyzman classifies negative emotionality physically as following: dissatisfaction, anguish, sadness, anger, suffering, resentment, fear, horror, pity, sympathy, regret, feelings of insult, hatred, coldness, envy, jealousy, enmity, malice, mistrust, shame, disgust, impatience, remorse, dishonesty, grumbling, etc. [3: 74]. We can also divide the occurrence of emotionality into three types: emotionality generated by the subject's internal feelings, emotional attitude, causative emotionality. If the emotionality, associated with the subject, is expressed through the feelings of a person, the emotional attitude refers to the feeling of the subject caused by an object, event, and also the emotions of the subject towards the object, and causative emotionality can be evaluated as the action of the person to make the addressee in a forced emotional state. Causative emotionality was chosen as the object of our analysis from the presented emotional signs. Causative emotionality is usually seen as the effect of the subject on the object. As it is mentioned, causative emotionality also has a negative and positive expression. Negative causative emotionality creates a situation that is unpleasant for a person (fear, anger, etc.). Syntactically, causation is "the experiencer participates syntactically as an object in the expression of an emotion" [4: 201-218].

The features of causativeness in the English language, related to emotional attitude, form a unique lexical-semantic field. This field is represented by:

- influencing the subject's psycho-emotional state in sentences involving causative-emotional verbs;

As the main predicate serves causative verb and the units that serve as the secondary predicate express emotional features;

- interaction of adverbs that indicate causative and emotional meaning.

In the function of a predicate, some verbs denoting an emotional attitude also have a causative meaning, which belong to the type of lexical causation, they serve to change or affect the internal expressive state of the subject.

RESULTS

In causative constructions, the emotional state of the subject in the function of a complement meets the causation in a certain sense or passes the function of the executor of that causation.

Morphological suffixes expressing causation not only acquire causative content, but can also form emotional semantic features. This process applies to the morphological suffixes of the compulsory voice (in Karakalpak: *feyildin ózgelik dárejesi*) in the Karakalpak language. These adverbs, in addition to performing grammatical functions, also express causative-emotional semantics.

It should be noted that the verbs of causative emotional attitude in the Karakalpak language have their own morphological characteristic. In particular, the suffixes such as *-t, -tyr, -tir, -dyr, -dir, -yr, -ir, -qyz, -kiz, -gyz, -giz, -qar, -ker* and auxiliary verbs *qiliw, etiw* that goes after adjectives have the characteristic of expressing causative emotional semantic meaning in the Karakalpak language. The verbs belonging to the class of verbs of emotional attitude, in addition to the subject's feelings towards the object, also have semantic meanings such as evaluating it, expressing different attitudes towards the object. For example:

1) – Достың жылатып айтады, душпан күлдирип айтады, - дегендей, биз саған доспыз. (М.Дарибаев, Мыңлардың бири, 31)

- 2) Турымбет бирден не дерин билмей тыгылды.
– Жумагүлди қайтадан алмақшымысан? - деди ол жигитти көп **қысындыра** бермейин деген ой менен. (Т.Кайыпбергенов, «Қарақалпақ қызы» романы, 210)
- 3) – Ишемен! Сизиң қолыңыздан шыққан хәр қандай суўсын мен ушын пал!
– О-о-о! Мени **қуўандырып** жибердиңиз! (М.Нызанов, «Соңғы тилек» романы, 68)
- 4) Жумагүлдің ашыўы Турымбеттиң салысын суўға кетирип, **сескендирди**. (Т.Кайыпбергенов, «Қарақалпақ қызы» романы, 102)
- 5) Хәр бириниң қолында бир-бирден ала таяғы бар екен. Төбелеске таяр киятырған жигитлер хәммени **таңландырды**. (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы. 400 б.)
- 6) Мурат шайықтың бул күлкиси жас жигитлерди йошланған үстине **йошландырды**. (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы, 227 б.)
- 7) – Қызым, мен сени өзимиздиң әмирге бермеймен, – деп кәрўан басы қызды **тынышландырды**. (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы. 269 б.)
- 8) Қоңсылас ханлықларға ара-тура шабыўыл жасап, зықын өткерип турды. Бул Иранның Нәдир шахын **тынышсызландырды**. (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы. 271 б.)
- 9) Биринши шақырымы менен екнши шақырымының арасын дым созып жиберди. Мениң шыдамдымы сынап көрип атырғандай **күйдирди** олар-әм. (М. Нызанов, 8-том, 134)

In the given examples, emotional verbs such as **күлдириў**, **қуўандырыў**, **таңландырыў**, **йошландырдыў**, **тынышландырыў**, **күйдирдиў** received **-дыр**, **-дир** causative suffixes according to the phonetic and phonological characteristics of the verb.

This indicates the diversity of the verb system in the Karakalpak language. Emphasized verbs are combined into one common causative emotional content when they take different suffixes. Causative emotionality covers the meaning of positive or negative impact on the mental state of the listener.

Causative emotional effect is carried out by adding morphological suffixes of another type in the verb group ending with a voiceless consonant. For example:

- 1) – Аманлық, - деди селқослаў даўыс пенен. - Билесең бе... Сен қарақалпақлардың «орта дәрмиян шаңарағы» болдың. Туўры Ешнйаз ахунға бар. Мени жиберди де. Жаңа шаңырақ болған адамның қалай жүрип-турыўын үйретеди.

Шайық басқа сөзге келмей алға жүрип кетти.

«Орта дәрмиян» деген сөз Аманлықты хәм **қуўантты**, хәм **муңайтты**. (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы. 180 б.)

2) Күтилмегенде ўәзир шақыртты. Бул шақырық оны бир жағынан **қорқытты** да. Өйткени, ўәзир әнейилик пенен шақырмайды. Сыйлық береді ямаса жазалайды. (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы. 315 б.)

3) – Инсанның мәнгилик еки жолдасы болар-мыш. Олар кимлер?

– Бири - хакыйқый досты, екншици - душпаны. Инсан усы еки жолдасын да дурыс түсинип, қыянетсиз, хеш кайсысын **өкпелетпей**, оларғада өзи өкпелемей жасаса, өмири тынышлықта өтеди. (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Қарақалпақпан, Тәўекелишмен. 88)

4) Турымбет бундай сораўларға бурынлары «жаман емес» деп әстен гана жуўап беретугын еди, хәзирги қуўанышы араласа берген жуўабы байды **қуўантты**. (Т.Кайыпбергенов, «Қарақалпақ қызы» романы, 76)

In the given examples, emotional verbs such as *қуўантты*, *муңайтты*, *қорқытты*, *өкпелетпей* received *-т*, *-ыт* causative suffixes according to the phonetic and phonological characteristics of the verb.

In the Karakalpak language, causative emotionality is formed by adding emphatic adverbs to the group of emotive verbs, and there are a number of forms that are expressed using analytical forms. For example:

1) *Ол ағасын қана қылып алғанына қатты өкиниште, бірақ, оны қалай жууып-шайуыдың есабын таппай ар-сар еди. (М. Нызанов, 8-том, 307)*

2) — *Жүриң, кеттик. Бахты тайған адам өзгени бахытлы қыла алмайды, - деди. (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы. 507 б.)*

3) *Бул сапары Маманды қайран қалдырған жағдай болажақ патшаның келбеті болды ... (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы. – 189 б.)*

The above-mentioned examples allow us to conclude that the elements representing causative emotionality are formed by lexical, morphological, and analytical means.

1) *She was glad, of course, that her sharp wit had let her escape from the men, but it **made** her angry. (Deveraux Jude, 5)*

2) *Shamrok Jolnes turned pale, but **forced** a smile. (O'Henry, 434)*

3) *His eyes were fixed upon Della, and there was an expression in them that she would not read, and it **terrified** her. (O'Henry, 4)*

In the first example, the person who acted as an object had a negative emotional reaction under the influence of external causation. In this example, the causative verb *make* and the adjective structure denoting an emotional state form causative emotionality. Causative emotionality in the following second and third examples was directly caused by the semantics of the verbs *force*, *terrify*. It shows that the causative emotionality in English is the traditional causative constructions i.e. **make, let, have +Obj. + adj./infinitive**, in addition to being expressed with the help of verbs with this characteristic. This indicates that causative emotionality has a lexical character in English.

DISCUSSION

Causality is not only between the subject and the addressee, but can cause the addressee to fall into an emotional state as a result of the impact of the event. Also, the negative or positive nature of the information in the events causes a negative or positive emotional state in the addressee. Causative emotionality is evaluated as an action that means that the subject brings the addressee into an emotional state under forced, unexpected circumstances.

Causative emotional action consists of direct subject (person, event, information, speech unit), addressee or object (person) and verb, verb combinations with causative semantics. In the general, we can see the construction of expression of causative emotionality in English and Karakalpak languages in the following tables:

Table № 1

In English
Caus.V + Obj
1) ... how skilfully he avoided anything that would embarrass her ; (Ch. Dickens, 472)
2) As I was looking out of window that same evening, it surprised me , and made me rather uneasy, to see Mr. Micawber and Uriah Heep walk past, arm in arm. (Ch. Dickens,

472)
1) If such goodness does not make her miserable now, she will never deserve to be happy! (J. Austen, <i>Pride and Prejudice</i> , 460)
2) She exerted herself, and did try to make her comfortable, by considering all that had passed ... (J. Austen, <i>Emma</i> , 270)
Caus. V + obj + emotional adj. or inf.
1) What made you so shy of me ... (J. Austen, <i>Pride and Prejudice</i> , 581)
2) ... and it has often made me smile to think how Alan's instinct awoke at the mere sight of it. (Robert Louis Stevenson, <i>Kidnapped</i> , 217)
3) 'But he paid her not the smallest attention till her grandfather's death made her mistress of this fortune.' (J. Austen, <i>Pride and Prejudice</i> , 232)

Table № 2

In Karakalpak
Объект + феъл + каузатив кўшимча -т, -тыр, -тир, -дыр, -дир, -ыр, -ир, -қыз, -киз, -ғыз, -ғиз, -қар, -кер
1) – Жумагүлди қайтадан алмақшымысан? - деди ол жигитти көп қысындыра бермейин деген ой менен. (Т.Кайпбергенов, «Қарақалпақ қызы» романы, 102)
2) Хәр бириниң қолында бир-бирден ала таяғы бар екен. Төбелеске таяр киятырған жигитлер хәммени таңландырды . (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы. 400)
Объект + сифат феъл
1) Бул сапары Маманды хайран қалдырған жағдай болажақ патшаның келбети болды ... (Т. Қайыпбергенов. Маман бий әпсанасы. 189)
2) Ол ағасын қапа қылып алғанына қатты өкиниште, бирақ, оны қалай жуўып-шайыўдың есабын таппай ар-сар еди. (М. Нызанов, 8-том, 307)

Positive and negative emotional causative verbs in the Karakalpak and English languages.

Table № 3

In Karakalpak
Positive: күлдириў, қуўандырыў, таңландырыў, йошландырыў, бахытлы қылыў, хайран қалдырыў;
Negative: жылатыў, қысындырыў, сескендириў, тынышландырыў, күйдириў, муңайтыў, қорқытыў, өкпелетиў, қапа қылыў.
In English
Positive: <i>surprise, make comfortable, make safe, make smile, make mistress;</i>
Negative: <i>make angry, forced, terrified, embarrass, make miserable, make shy.</i>

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of causative emotionality in English and Karakalpak shows that the positive causative emotionality has the semantics of intentionality in a certain sense. Also, the causation of the subject in order to influence the addressee also represents intentional causative emotionality. Causative emotionality expressed in these languages differs from a structural, morphological point of view (of course, emotional causativeness can be understood with specific differences in linguistic cultures).

REFERENCES

1. Булгакова Ю.С., Особенности вербализации отрицательных эмоций в английском и испанском языках. – Москва. 2009. МГОУ. Вестник. – С. 110-115.
2. Богданова Л.И., Русский глагол: эмоции, оценки, сочетаемость // Эмоции в языке и речи / Под ред. И.А.Шаронова. – М., 2005. – С 31-41; Wierzbicka A. Emotions across languages and cultures. – Cambridge, 1999.
3. Гройсман Л.А., Медицинская психология. – М.: «Аванта», 1995. - С. 74.
4. Michaela Porn., Psychophysical and Physical Causative Emotion Verbs in Finnish: The Temporal Structure of Causative Emotion Verb + Infinitive 1 // Constructions within Conceptual Semantics. SKY Journal of Linguistics 21. 2008. – P. 201–218.
5. Дарибаев М., Мыңлардың бири. – Нөкис: , Қарақалпақстан баспасы, 1974. – 136 б.
6. Кайпбергенов Т. Шығармалары 5 томлық, 4-том, «Қарақалпақ қызы» романы. – Нөкис: Қарақалпақстан баспасы, 1980. – 500 б.
7. Нызанов М., «Таңламалы шығармалары, VIII, Роман, гүрриңлер, драббллер». – Нөкис: «Билим», 2018. – 302 б.
8. Қайыпбергенов Т., Қарақалпақ дәстаны. Маман бий эпсанасы. – Нөкис: «Билим» баспасы, 2018-жыл. – 512 б.
9. Кайпбергенов Т., Қарақалпақпан. Тәуекелшімен романы. – Нөкис: «Билим», 2003. – 528 б.
10. Deveraux J., The awakening. – New York: POCKET BOOKS, 1988. – P. 231.
11. Dickens Ch., David Copperfield. ebook by Planet PDF. <http://www.planetpdf.com/> – P. 1307.
12. O’Henry, 100 Selected Stories, – Hertfordshire: Wordsworth Editions Limited Cumberland House. 1995. – P. 735.
13. Austen J., Emma. ebook by Planet PDF. <http://www.planetpdf.com/>. – P. 745.
14. Austen J., Pride and Prejudice, ebook by Planet PDF. <http://www.planetpdf.com/>. – P. 593.